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Review Article

Bridging the Visual Gap: Low Vision Devices as Tools for Educational and Behavioral Progress in Children

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ABSTRACT

Background: Children with visual impairment often face significant challenges in education, social interactions and it can hinder the academic performances, social engagement and even psychological well-being. To address these barriers, Low Vision Devices (LVDs) have emerged as an effective tool to enhance learning, interact and function independently. This review explores the impacts of low vision devices on educational and behavioral outcomes in children with visual impairment. Purpose: This literature review evaluates the role of LVDs in terms of education and behavior outcomes in children (3-18 years) with visual impairments by interpreting technologies or devices and training programs to enhance the learning, social competence and quality of life. Methods: A structured review literature search was conducted using PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate, covering publications from 2000 to 2025. Inclusion criteria were focused on studies evaluating educational performance, reading ability, and behavioral or social outcomes associated with LVDs use. Adult-only studies and non-original research were excluded. A total of 14 studies were studied. Data were extracted on study design, population characteristics, types of LVDs used, and reported outcomes. Results: Educational interventions involving LVDs have demonstrated improvements in academic performance, visual functioning, reading speed and comprehension. Assistive technology like braille, tactile maps, screen screen-reading software supports in the development of education programs. Assistive technologies, including LVDs, are among the most effective tools for improving learning outcomes in low- and middle-income countries. Behavioral outcomes have also shown improved social competence and social behaviors. Conclusions: Integrating LVDs and associated training programs significantly improves the educational and behavioral outcomes among children with visual impairments, contributing to greater independence and

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quality of life for these children.

INTRODUCTION

Vision plays an important role in a child's educational, social development and overall development. If a child has visual impairment, he or she may face challenges and barriers in his or her activities; therefore, it is crucial to assess vision early in order to protect them from unwanted conditions. Avoidable and preventable visual impairment can be saved if the vision is assessed and detected earlier at a young age (Rukwaro et al. 2018; Dube et al.,2024). Visual Impairment is a boarder spectrum of sight loss and can be defined as a condition encompassing partial sight to blindness.

The term Low vision means visual acuity 3/60 to <6/18 in the better eye after best corrected visual acuity (BCVA) in the better eye and visual field (VF) <20 degrees from the point of fixation. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines the term blindness as corrected visual acuity in the better eye of <10/200 and severe visual impairment as corrected visual acuity in the better eye of <20/200 but equal to or better than 10/200 (Dube et al.,2024). Low vision devices such as magnifiers, telescopes and other assistive devices help to decrease the challenges and barriers faced by children with visual impairments. LVDs are useful in appropriately and also a life-changing and shaping tool that is made for those with visual impairment to help them see in maximize their potential. It can be used singly or as a combination in order to perform their desired tasks and also to most extent helps to overcome any challenges and barriers in terms of education, social, and emotional aspects, and even psychological well-being (Nazir & Ali, 2024). There are different forms and types of LVDs that can help and give enormous advantages to a visually impaired person. They can choose the devices according to

their needs, or they can be prescribed according to their effect and degree of impaired vision. The types are optical devices, non-optical devices, electronic LVDs and complex devices using advanced technologies. Some of them are illuminated and non-illuminated hand-held magnifiers, illuminated and non-illuminated stand magnifiers, Single vision spectacle magnifiers, Dome magnifiers, talking watch, Monocular telescope, Video magnifiers, CCTV, large print books, black dark bold tip pen and line books for better contrast, cap, dark curtains for control of glare etc. can improve their aspects on good and positive terms like social skills, knowledges and help in reducing dependency. Environment modification can also improve a lot in their vision.

Education acts as a fundamental right as it increases the learning capacities for visually impaired students and also for critical thinking and independent living skills (Bratanovic et al., 2024). LVDs support the idea of improving the reading ability, which may result in good academic performance (Rukwaro et al., 2018). Lack of Social skills development can give a negative impression on building peer relationships, friends and even in education (Caballo et al., 2007). Children with visual impairment can face difficulty in forming social interactions and relationships (Cappagli et al, 2018). There is a study supporting that assistive devices in education make children more accessible and allow them to participate more actively, especially in classroom settings (Nazir & Ali, 2024). The use of LVDs has approved children with disabilities improve their social activities, cognitive function, enhancing their well-being and so on. However, even though these facilities are available, there are still challenges and barriers, such as affordability, lack of awareness, and insufficient training, while using the LVDs still remains.

Prevalence

Visual impairments are quite common in India and need to be considered in this ongoing matter. Globally, there are estimated to be 37 million, of which 1.4M blind children, almost three-quarters of them live in developing countries (Magdalene et al.,2021). India has an estimated 320,000 blind children, which calculates to be the highest no of blind as compared with other countries (Acharjee et al., 2008). The prevalence of blindness in children ranges approximately 0.3/1000 children in wealthy regions to 1.5/1000 within the poorest regions (Acharjee et al., 2008; Magdalene et al.,2021). But the prevalence can vary across different countries as factors such as health care socio socioeconomic status, prevalence of chronic disease, and environmental conditions may influence the epidemiology of visual impairment. According to WHO, at the beginning of the VISION 2020 program, above 19 million children, below 15 years, were visually impaired and 1.4 million children had irreversible blindness (Gilbert & Foster et al., 2001). The program has been enriched to provide a good and positive impact on prevention, management and control of visual impairment.

METHODS

A structured literature search was conducted to identify studies evaluating the impact of low vision devices (LVDs) on educational and behavioural outcomes in children with visual impairment. The databases searched included PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate, covering publications from 2000 to 2025. This review includes peer-reviewed articles and institutional reports focusing on children aged 3–18 years with visual impairment, specifically studies evaluating educational performance, reading ability, and behavioural or social outcomes associated with low vision device

(LVD) use. It excludes studies solely on adults, non-original research such as editorials or commentaries. A total of 14 studies were selected after screening titles, abstracts, and full texts. Data were extracted on study design, population characteristics, types of LVDs used, and reported outcomes.

RESULTS

Educational interventions involving low vision devices (LVDs) have demonstrated significant improvements in academic performance and visual functioning. (Rukwaro et al. 2018; Dube et al.,2024) reported notable gains in reading speed and comprehension following structured training with LVDs. (Hunt et al. 2025) emphasized that assistive technologies, including LVDs, are among the most effective tools for improving learning outcomes in low- and middle-income countries. In support of this term, a different study also supports that there was an improvement in the areas of visual perception after doing educational rehabilitation intended for the assessment of visual motor integration, visual perception and motor coordination thereby suggesting the need to implement an educational rehabilitation program for the student with visual impairment (Bratanovic et al., 2024; Lovie-Kitchin et al., 2001).

In addition to the educational outcomes improvement by using assistive technology, another study supports that the use of assistive technology helps to achieve the desired educational outcomes by helping to resolve the educational problems. In this, the study used different types of assistive technology like braille, tactile maps, glasses, CCTV cameras, screen reading software and a white cane. The use of braille turns out to be the most commonly used assistive technology and supports the development of education programs (Nazir & Ali, 2024).

Beyond academic or educational measures, behavioural and social outcomes have also shown positive trends. Structured interventions using LVDs were associated with improved social competence and pro-social behaviours, as highlighted by (Ivy et al. 2016; Magdalene et al. 2021), further noted enhancements in peer interaction, self-confidence, and mental health among children using assistive devices. Another study supporting behavioral outcomes found that children with visual impairment can enhance their social and behavioral skills after proposing an intervention study by an experimenter and participant with the experiment while performing freehand movements using sonorous feedback on the experimenter's wrist. After 12 weeks, it improved after using the bracelet (Cappagli et al., 2018).

Thus, Low Vision Devices appear to have significantly improved the levels of educational, behavioural and social outcomes in visual impairment through these studies. Hence, it appears to be more beneficial if the low vision care is integrated into the lives of visual impairment children especially school-going children tend to get more benefits in terms of their educational purposes.

Background and causes

Visual impairment can arise from various factors affecting children. It may affect the child's development, which can persist throughout life. Factors include congenital cataracts, refractive errors, retinal disorders, developmental delays, systemic related eye diseases, genetic conditions, acquired such as trauma, injury or infections etc.

A study from northeastern India indicates a high incidence of childhood blindness, often

preventable and treatable cases (Acharjee et al., 2008). Another study suggests that visual impairment in children can be impaired from enhancing relevant social behavior skills, leading to decrease in chances for personal growth and independence (Caballo et al., 2007), (Magdalene et al., 2021). The prevalence of visual impairment in India due to congenital cataracts are 1.03/10,000 and incidence are 1.8 to 3.6/10,000 per year (Khokhar, 2017). The prevalence of visual impairment in India from Congenital Glaucoma are 1 in 3,3300 live births. (Sirisha Senthil, 2019).

Barriers and challenges

Despite the upcoming technologies or low vision devices, there are still barriers and challenges that hinder in developing the educational, behavioral outcomes and others. There are difficulties like cost of the devices, technology availability, lack of awareness, social stigma, lack of training, institutional support, product distribution and so on. These factors lead many children with visual impairment are face many challenges in engaging in positive social interaction, giving rise to feelings of frustration, depression, anxiety, loneliness, etc. (Cappagli et al., 2018).

In terms of education, children with visual impairments may have encountered obstacles like untrained teachers, lack of reading and writing materials, limited access to devices for low vision, lack of funding and resources. studies have shown that supplying adequate and appropriate devices and training to learners can improve the outcomes and hence improve in education field for such patients. Neglect and insufficient resources can limit their potential abilities (Rukwaro et al., 2018).

The use of LVDs has enabled children with disabilities to improve their social activities, cognitive function, and enhance their well-being

and so on. But they may find it difficult to interact with people, use visual cues and may have poor self-confidence. A sense of family burden may be in their mind, which may lead to depression, fears, and anxiety that can happen anytime (Ivy et al., 2016; Caballo et al., 2007; Magdalene et al., 2021).

Future directions

Many studies have been focusing and aiming to improve and to enhance the effectiveness and accessibility of low vision devices, but still there are gaps that exist. Some studies are saying that there is a clear need for integrating more interventions with social and behavioral development (Cappagli et al., 2018), (Ivy et al., 2016). Long-term studies are necessary to assess the effectiveness and impact of low vision devices on educational and behavioral outcomes, academic performances and mental health. Research on children with visual impairments with Disabilities, especially in low-income and middle-income families, is neglected and further studies are required in order to improve their functioning, skills, competencies, quality of life and many more (Hunt et al., 2025). More rehabilitation methods, with more exercise therapy, newer low vision aids, and CCTV, also need to be implemented (Lee & Cho, 2007).

CONCLUSIONS

This review indicates that vision devices can be a life-changing changing to children with visual impairments. The devices help build up confidence, independence, improve reading skills, making learning materials more accessible and enhances peer interactions. Not only they improving in communication skills but also helps in building up strong connections and boost emotional well-being. Even there is improvement in some areas, there are still remains with barriers

and challenges that the children with visual impairments face like lack of awareness, cost, availability of devices, training, trained learners etc. Moving forward, long terms studies can help us to know more about the ongoing issues and even help in children with visual impairments with disabilities. By working together, we can do more study and apply more interventions for better outcomes and creating a more inclusive and supportive environment for these children with visual impairments.

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